

Dynamic Effects and Interfacial Crack Propagation

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, dynamic effects during propagation of a deflected crack are explored. Experimental evidence from a sandwich specimen of SiC layers separated by a thin graphitic interface is presented. These results, in the form of crack advance data and crack speed measurements, confirm that interfacial crack propagation can involve dynamic effects, which significantly influence the energy available to propagate the cracks. It is shown that a consideration of crack history is necessary to predict the strain energy release rate accurately at any point.

1. INTRODUCTION

The premise of fracture mechanics is the conservation of energy during failure. Griffith¹ proposed in 1920 that the elastic energy released and the work done by the loading system as the crack extended should be balanced with a surface energy term. During a conference at Cambridge University in 1945, Mott² considered the kinetic energy accumulated in a material during the propagation of a crack. He showed from simple energy arguments that, during brittle fracture, the crack could be expected to tend towards a value of the order of the velocity of sound in the material, with the associated kinetic energy being appreciable. In order for kinetic energy to be accumulated during failure, an excess of energy must be released over and above that required to generate new surfaces. Certain geometries of crack propagation are particularly conducive to this. Consider a crack in a tensile sheet specimen loaded under displacement control. The locus of failure for such a sample is shown in Fig.1. The point where the stress strain curve for the sample intersects Fig. 1, is the point at which failure is predicted. It can be seen that there is a region of this curve, in the positive gradient region, where, as soon as failure starts, it will be predicted to continue. Indeed, what Berry^{3,4} predicted in 1960, is that, as the crack extends in this unstable region it accumulates kinetic energy, which can then be made available later to drive crack propagation beyond the static equilibrium position. This is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The energy released during failure can often exceed the critical value strictly necessary to propagate the crack. In order to predict crack arrest, a consideration of the scope for storage and subsequent release of kinetic energy is essential. For monolithic ceramics, crack arrest rarely occurs. However, some consideration of the problem has been made. In 1969, Hasselman⁵ considered thermal shock resistance. He proposed that catastrophic failure could be avoided if the total elastic energy in the material were less than the total fracture energy required to fail across the whole specimen. In other words, he proposed an energy balance over the whole of a crack propagation event. This allows for storage of any excess elastic energy during initial stages of crack propagation, which can then be made available to continue crack propagation later. He showed that a heavily cracked material is less susceptible to catastrophic failure caused by dynamic effects than a sound material. Evans⁶

subsequently concluded that a more satisfactory approach than Hasselman's global energy balance is to use a modified, smaller value of K_{IC} for crack arrest. This can explain any crack overshoot that may be observed when $K_I < K_{IC}$, although it does not obviously reflect the physical situation.

Figure 1: The locus of failure for the Griffith condition. For a sample under displacement control that fails at A, as the crack grows, the stress will drop. Hence the crack is predicted to continue extending. As it extends, the excess elastic energy released is stored as kinetic energy and can enable the crack to be driven beyond point C to D, where areas ABC and CDE are equal⁴.

Figure 2: Crack deflection geometry used by Kendall. Comparing (a) and (b) illustrates that an interface is constrained from growing until the outer layer has effectively failed. Hence G_I may exceed G_{IC} at the point of deflection.

For ceramic composites, the prediction of crack arrest is generally of interest. For the vast majority of ceramic composites, crack deflection at an interface is a necessary condition to maintain the integrity of the component. With this in mind, the present paper considers the existence of kinetic effects during crack deflection events.

2. BACKGROUND THEORY

2.1 Crack Deflection

Since Cook and Gordon⁷ first proposed in 1964 that crack deflection could act as a toughening mechanism, there has been interest in deriving an energy based criterion to predict crack deflection. In 1975, Kendall⁸ performed an elegant series of crack deflection experiments using brittle rubbers. The geometry of his experiments is illustrated in Fig. 2. He found that the ratio of interfacial toughness to bulk toughness required for successful crack deflection varied between 0.11 and 0.18. Consider Kendall's sample: when applying a load to this sample, there will come a point when, if the outer layer were free to debond (c.f. Fig. 2(a) and 2(b)), there would be sufficient elastic energy released by the interfacial crack propagating to generate the new interfaces. However, the interfacial crack can only propagate when the outer layer has failed. This means that the whole system will remain intact until a load is reached which is sufficient to fail the outer layer. At this point, the through thickness crack will propagate until it reaches the interface. Hence, at the point of crack deflection, both the through thickness crack and the deflected crack can have more than enough energy to propagate. This suggests the possibility for kinetic effects to be important during crack deflection events. Existing treatments of crack deflection⁹ have considered a through thickness crack which is propagating in a stable manner when it encounters the interface. This situation would seem unlikely for the majority of brittle systems.

An additional point concerns an observation made in the work of Kendall. In his paper on crack deflection, he observed that, near the limiting ratio of toughnesses required for successful crack deflection, it was often observed that both the through thickness crack and the deflected crack began to propagate with one subsequently dominating. This might imply that crack deflection is dependant on kinetic effects: whichever crack propagates fastest begins to dominate. A combination of the above points have led to the investigation of dynamic effects during crack deflection in a simple and common geometry, which is described below.

2.2 The Mechanics of Failure during Three Point Bend

The geometry of the current crack deflection experiments is illustrated in Fig.3. In this section the strain energy release rates for both the through thickness crack and the deflected cracks are discussed. The strain energy release rate or stress intensity factors for a partially cracked beam loaded in three point bend is widely available in the literature^{10,11}. From such expressions, a variation of compliance with notch depth can be established.

Figure 3: (a) Geometry of the specimens used. Note that the thin graphitic interface does not extend right to the end of the specimen (b) Specimen midway through testing in three point bend. The sequence of events involves the upper layer failing, the interfacial crack growing and then the interfacial crack growing right to the end of the interface. Failure occurs by the bottom layer failing at that point.

Figure 4: The variation of strain energy release rates for both the penetrating crack and the interfacial cracks as they extend. Note that G exceeds G_c for both types of crack at the point of crack deflection. If the excess energy being released cannot be recovered then the crack will stop at the zero recovery point. If it can be recovered then the interfacial crack will extend further until the energy released over the entire cracking event is equal to that required to generate the new interfaces (full recovery).

The quasi-static strain energy release rate: G_i for a deflected crack, travelling parallel to the length of the beam (see Fig 3), is less well documented. It has recently been derived and experimentally verified for a well developed interfacial crack^{12,13}. Expressions for specimen compliance: C and G_i are given below:

$$C = \frac{-1}{2 \Sigma_1} \left[\left(\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Sigma_2} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{a^3}{3} + L^2 a - L a^2 \right) - \frac{L^3 \Sigma_1}{3 \Sigma_2} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$G_i = \frac{-P^2}{8b} \left(\frac{1}{\Sigma_2} - \frac{1}{\Sigma_1} \right) (a^2 - 2La + L^2) \quad (2)$$

where P = load, Σ_1 = beam stiffness ($=EI$) for the base section, Σ_2 = beam stiffness for the entire section, b = specimen width + see Fig. 3. These equations enable the variation of compliance to be predicted as either type of crack propagates. In turn, this means that the load can be predicted for a known, imposed displacement, which can then be used to predict the strain energy release rates. The variation of strain energy release rates with crack advance are plotted in Fig.4 for a typical test specimen.

Two points may be noted from Fig.4. Firstly, in an identical argument to that used by Berry⁴, it might be expected that during the stages of crack propagation in which the strain energy release rate exceeds the critical value, the excess may contribute to kinetic energy of the debonding flanks. If this energy can then be made available later to continue crack propagation, then substantially longer crack lengths are expected than those predicted from a criterion neglecting kinetic effects. The predicted crack length from a static (or zero energy recovery) criterion, is compared with that from a dynamic (full energy recovery) criterion in Fig.4. Note that it is assumed that G_{ic} values are independent of crack speed. Although this is not always the case, for the brittle system considered in this study, no effect of crack speed on G_{ic} has been found. Secondly, it should be possible to equate the excess energy released during the initial stages of the test to kinetic energy of the crack flanks and hence estimate the crack speeds expected. With these points in mind, the following experiments were undertaken to measure crack lengths and crack speeds during crack deflection events.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Crack Length Experiments

The specimen geometry was a simple sandwich arrangement as illustrated in Fig.3. Production¹⁴ was by a viscous processing route in which a SiC powder was mixed with an aqueous polymer solution. This dough was then extruded and shaped. Finally it was sintered without pressure at 2100°C. The approximate dimensions of the resulting specimens were 40mm by 2.5mm wide and 2mm total thickness. Specimens were notched using a diamond coated wire saw to a variety of depths. These were then tested in three point bend (see Fig.3) with a half loading span of 19mm under displacement control. Ramp rates used were 100µm per minute. Interfacial toughness data have been obtained in a variety of ways and is described elsewhere¹³.

Figure 5: The loading arrangement to measure interfacial crack speed. By timing the interval between the electrical strips being broken, an estimate of the interfacial crack speed can be obtained. It is assumed that the time for the through thickness crack to travel is negligible. This is because the interfacial crack is fixed by the specimen geometry to be over ten times longer.

3.2 Crack Speed Experiments

The arrangement for measuring crack speeds is illustrated in Fig.5. Specimen production is as above. These specimens were coated on the top and bottom surfaces with conductive silver paint. An estimate of the crack speed was obtained by applying a potential across these strips and recording the time difference between the two strips breaking during failure.

Ramp rates were 300 μm per minute with testing again being performed under displacement control.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 General features

A number of interesting points arise from inspection of the load/displacement plots recorded during the crack length experiments described above. A typical plot is shown in Fig. 6. Firstly, it should be noted that the height of the peak load will be determined by the depth of the notch. Secondly, it can be seen that there is a linear region immediately after the load drop. This corresponds to a constant compliance, which indicates that no interfacial cracking can be occurring. Now consider Fig.3 again. If the interfacial crack had stopped at the length corresponding to the zero recovery criterion (as soon as G_i dropped below G_{ic}) then when the load next increased, G_i would increase and interfacial cracking would be expected to continue immediately. However, if the full recovery criterion were obeyed, then the interfacial crack would extend to a region where G_i has substantially dropped below G_{ic} and hence the load would have to increase substantially before cracking could recontinue^{15,16}. This is what is observed in Fig.6 and provides strong evidence for dynamic effects occurring during crack deflection events. The compliance of the specimen subsequent to the load drop can lead to an indication of how far the crack has propagated, as can the load at which interfacial cracking restarts. These procedures are described in more detail in 3.2.

Figure 6: A typical load/displacement plot for a specimen being tested as in Fig.3(b). The presence of a linear region after the load drop is strong evidence for interfacial crack overshoot, i.e. beyond the zero recovery position shown in Fig.4. Since the interfacial crack length is known to be equal to the length of the interface at the point of ultimate failure, then comparison of this value with that predicted at the point of failure can lead to a calibration of the crack length measurements (see 4.2.3)

By varying the strength of the SiC layers (by notching), it has been possible to vary the load on the sample at the point of crack deflection. This means that G_i is also varied at the time of crack deflection (see eqn.2). From Fig.3, it can be seen that, if the value of G_i is high enough over the initial stages of interfacial crack propagation, the full recovery criterion can predict that the interfacial crack should extend right to the end of the specimen. The zero recovery criterion can never predict this, since G_i must drop to zero (eqn.2) as the interfacial crack approaches the loading points (neglecting significant shear effects). In order to investigate this, a specimen was generated such that the end of the interface was just outside the loading points. When this un-notched specimen was loaded up, the through-thickness crack began to propagate, was successfully deflected and the interfacial crack extended right along the interface to beyond the loading point. The bottom layer of SiC then failed. In the region close to and beyond the loading point, there is no other energy available to propagate the crack apart from kinetic energy of the ligament. The observation of failure in such a region again provides convincing evidence for the existence of kinetic effects. This result also illustrates the limitations of describing dynamic effects by assuming that a reduced critical stress intensity factor is required for crack arrest. It would be necessary to have a negative value of this parameter in order to predict this result, which would imply that once an interfacial crack is propagating, it could never stop. Since stable interfacial crack growth has been observed, this is plainly non physical.

Both of these observations confirm that dynamic effects are certainly occurring during crack deflection.

Figure 7: Comparison of the interfacial crack lengths expected as a function of failure load on the sample for both the zero recovery criterion and the full recovery. It can be seen that the experimentally determined values lie in-between these two limits. This indicates that some energy recovery is occurring, but that it is not 100% efficient.

4.2 Crack Length Measurement

For the stiff and opaque specimens used in this study, the determination of crack position from direct observation, even using in situ SEM testing, is very difficult. Several methods for determining crack position are available from the load displacement data. Consider the example of a typical load displacement plot shown in Fig.6. The two readings of interest are the compliance subsequent to the load drop and the load at which the plot becomes non-linear subsequent to the load drop.

4.2.1 Load Drop Method

When the interfacial crack bursts along the interface, the further the crack propagates, the larger the compliance and hence the larger the load drop. Therefore, by recording the value of the load drop an estimate of the interfacial crack length can be obtained. The equation for the compliance of the partially failed beam is given earlier (equation 1). Hence, by measuring the compliance of the beam at the point at which the crack burst has just stopped, rearranging equation 3 can give a value of crack length.

4.2.2 Repropagation Method

After the interfacial crack burst, corresponding to the observed load drop in the load displacement plot, there comes a point when the load has increased to a high enough value to continue interfacial crack propagation, ie G has become more than G_{ic} where G is given in equation 2. It can be seen from this equation that, for constant G_{ic} , the value of the load required to continue crack propagation increases for a longer interfacial crack length. Hence an indication of the length of the interfacial crack can be obtained by equating G to G_{ic} (which is known with some confidence) at the point at which crack propagation restarts and solving for interfacial crack length.

4.2.3 Calibration

The repropagation method can be simply verified using the procedure outlined below. If samples are generated with partial interfaces, see Figs.3 and 5, then at the point at which the interfacial crack reaches the end of the interface, it would be expected that the crack path will no longer be constrained and the specimen will fail. Hence, if the length of the interface is known, then the load required to propagate an interfacial crack of that particular length can be recorded from measuring the load when complete failure occurs. This enables a verification of the crack length measurements as outlined above. Comparing the predicted crack lengths at failure with the actual crack lengths shows that the average error is less than 1mm with the maximum error recorded for 7 such measurements being 1.6mm.

4.2.4 Comparison with Theory

Having measured the interfacial crack lengths subsequent to a crack deflection event, the results can be compared with the predictions of the two theories: full recovery of the kinetic energy stored in the specimen or zero energy recovery. The results of this procedure are shown in Fig.7. Here it can be seen that substantial kinetic energy must have been released to drive crack propagation beyond the static equilibrium position. However, some of the kinetic energy has been lost, since the cracks did not propagate to the maximum length predicted by the full recovery criterion.

4.3 Crack Speed Analysis

4.3.1 Crack Speed Predictions

It has been shown earlier in this paper, that the initial stages of interfacial crack propagation are accompanied by the release of an excess of energy. It was proposed that this energy is stored as kinetic energy of the debonding ligament. In order to investigate this proposal, some interfacial crack speeds have been measured. By assuming that the excess energy released during the initial period of crack propagation is stored as kinetic energy of the debonding ligaments, a rotational speed can be assigned to the ligament. By obtaining a relationship between crack position and ligament position, it is possible to assign a crack speed to this ligament speed. Due to space limitations, this procedure will be described in more detail elsewhere¹⁷.

Figure 8: Comparison of the measured value of crack speed with that predicted from the full energy recovery criterion. It should be noted that the measured value is an average of three measurements ranging from 5.3 km s^{-1} to 2.7 km s^{-1} . Although the scatter is considerable, the measurements do confirm that the speeds are broadly consistent with the hypothesis that significant kinetic energy is contained in the debonding ligaments.

4.3.2 Crack Speed Calculations

The results of the above procedure are shown in Figs 8. This shows the predicted crack speed as a function of crack length. It can be seen that the mean value is predicted to be between 4 and 5 km s^{-1} . Comparing this with the measured mean value over the first 11 mm of 3.7 km s^{-1} shows that the two are broadly consistent. This supports the hypothesis that significant proportions of the released energy can be stored as kinetic energy of the debonding crack flanks.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

(a) This paper has explored the possibility of significant kinetic effects during crack propagation subsequent to crack deflection. The experiments involve a simple crack deflection geometry in three point bend. Strong evidence has been presented for the existence of dynamic effects. This involves crack length measurements and some observations from the recorded load/displacement plot.

(b) It has been deduced that kinetic effects can lead to an increase in crack driving force, rather than a decrease in crack resistance. Two experiments have confirmed this. Firstly, interfacial cracks have been observed to propagate in a regime where the driving force can only have been provided by the kinetic energy of the crack flanks. Secondly, the kinetic

energy stored in the crack flanks (estimated via crack speed measurements) is of the order of magnitude needed to account for the observed crack advance.

(c) The strain energy release rate of an advancing crack is thus dependant on both the current rate of elastic energy release and any excess energy released earlier in the crack advance sequence which has been stored as kinetic energy of the crack flanks. Hence a consideration of crack history is, in general, necessary to accurately predict the current crack driving force.

(d) For brittle materials, crack growth is usually unstable. Hence, more energy is released than is needed to propagate the crack. Provided that a non-dissipative method of energy storage is available, this energy can subsequently contribute to driving the crack. This contribution will tend to be more significant in low toughness materials. In addition, this energy may be important when devising a criterion for crack deflection in brittle systems.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank ICI for financial support for one of us (AJP). A number of useful discussions have taken place with Dr. S.J.Howard of Cambridge University and Professor K.Kendall of Keele University.

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